

Supplementary Material

Prenatal Human Milk Oligosaccharides (HMOs) in context of BMI, gestational weight gain and lipid profiles – an association study in pregnant women with overweight or obesity

Supplementary table 1. HMOs and lipid parameters per time point in the total study sample.

Time point	2'FL (AUC) Median (IQR)	LDFT (AUC) Median (IQR)	3'SL (AUC) Median (IQR)	3'SLN (AUC) Median (IQR)
15 weeks, n=87	0.02 (0.01, 0.09)	0.02 (0.00, 0.03)	0.12 (0.10, 0.14)	0.02 (0.02, 0.03)
24 weeks, n=83	0.13 (0.03, 0.29)*	0.05 (0.01, 0.10)*	0.17 (0.13, 0.27)*	0.04 (0.03, 0.06)*
32 weeks, n=68	0.19 (0.06, 0.37)*§	0.08 (0.01, 0.15)*§	0.20 (0.16, 0.24)*	0.04 (0.03, 0.05)*
	Total cholesterol (mmol/L) Mean ± SD	HDL (mmol/L) Mean ± SD	LDL (mmol/L) Mean ± SD	Triglycerides (mmol/L) Mean ± SD
15 weeks, n=86	5.03 ± 0.88	1.75 ± 0.37	2.59 ± 0.80	1.54 ± 0.50
24 weeks, n=85	5.44 ± 0.97*	1.84 ± 0.42*	2.80 ± 0.91*	1.78 ± 0.56*
32 weeks, n=71	5.91 ± 1.05*§	1.75 ± 0.37§	3.14 ± 1.02*§	2.26 ± 0.66*§

*p< 0.001 compared to 15 weeks; §p< 0.001 compared to 24 weeks; AUC, area under the curve, IQR, interquartile range

Supplementary figure 1. Lipid concentrations over the course of pregnancy stratified by BMI < 35kg/m² and BMI ≥ 35kg/m². Box-and-whisker plots show concentrations in mmol/L for triglycerides, total cholesterol, LDL, and HDL separately for BMI groups at different time points during pregnancy. *p < 0.05; ns, not significant.